

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

100 Babasahin Para kay Fino: Intervention in the Development of Reading Comprehension

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino as an intervention to improve the reading comprehension level of students. Through the intervention of reading and developing the level of understanding of what the students read. The Quasi-Experimental, a group (one group) design pre-test, and post-test (pre-reading assessment and post-reading assessment) was used. The researchers have innovated from a simple reading method to the development of self-made reading materials containing to develop the level of understanding of what the students read. This study has proven that 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino is beneficial at developing students' reading comprehension.

Keywords: 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino; Reading Comprehension; Frustration; Instructional and independent level

1. Introduction

The Philippines is ranked 79th in the world, according to the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) report from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). 79 nations participated, and our country's average score on the reading evaluation was 340 in Reading Assessment. PISA includes "reading" as one of its emphasis topics (PISA, 2019).

Based on the general results released by the 3Bs Initiative of Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa under DepEd Memorandum No. 173 s. 2019, many students still lack reading skills. Also, many students do not understand Mathematics and Science lessons due to low reading comprehension skills (DepEd, 2019).

Paguio (2018) added that many experts believe that the number of students who are interested in reading books, magazines or newspapers is decreasing. In such activities they express personal purpose, ability, learning and understanding.

Meta-analysis including 17 studies from 2000 to 2016 was carried out by Kong, Seo, and Zhai (2018), the results showed that reading on paper was more effective than reading from digital gadgets.

According to research by Aquino et al. (2018), non-readers need to have sufficient study materials to pass challenging exams in a variety of areas. The authors proposed that to preserve their reading skills, particularly in terms of a thorough grasp of Filipino texts, intervention, innovation, and strategy are required.

According to Ulrich Ludewig et al. (2022), reading is one of the macro-skills or skills neglected in the learning aspect. Associated with the reading problem is the more aggressive challenge of continuing to guide students with low reading

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comprehension amid the pandemic. In fact, based on the recorded data of Bantay Basa of Rosario National High School for the academic year 2021-2022. As reported, 54% were in frustrated level, 25% were in instructional level and 15% were independent level, while the remaining 6% were recorded as dropping out. Based on the data gathered, it clearly shows that there is a problem that deserves attention and because of this, 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino was created.

The 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino is consist of 100 reading original works by teachers from the Filipino Department of Rosario National High School. This project gave students the opportunity to broaden their knowledge and develop their understanding of what they read.

This study intended to assess the effectiveness of 100 Babasahin para kay Fino as a reading intervention in the development of reading comprehension among grade seven students in Rosario National High School.

- What is the students' reading comprehension level based on the pre-reading assessment?
- What is the students' reading comprehension level based on the post-reading Assessment?
- Is there a significant difference in the level of reading comprehension of the student based on to the pre-reading assessment and the post-reading assessment after using 100 Babasahin Para Kay Fino?

2. Material and methods

This research used the Quasi-experimental using Pre-test and Post-test design. The Participants were Grade 7 students and selected using purposive sampling. The researcher used the Test of significance for the difference between Two Means using Paired T-test.

3. Results

Table 1 Results of Pre-reading Assessment

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pre-test	25	2.7600	1.1648

The participants obtained a 2.7600 mean, 1.1648 standard deviation in the pre-reading assessment. This result shows that the reading comprehension level is low.

Table 2 Results of Post-reading Assessment

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Post-test	25	9.8800	0.3317

The participants obtained a 9.8800 mean, 0.3317 standard deviation in the post-reading assessment. This result shows that the participants' reading comprehension level increased after using 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino.

Table 3 Comparison of Pre-reading Assessment and Post-reading Assessment Results

	P-value	Interpretation
Pre-test	0.000	Significant
Post-test		

The participants recorded a .000 significant value. The result shows that there is a significant difference in the level of students' reading comprehension after using the intervention 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino.

4. Discussions

Findings of this study showed that reading intervention were able to improve the level of reading comprehension after using 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino.

Based on the study's findings, it is proposed that school leaders and administrators spearhead programs that may increase the level of reading comprehension of all students by incorporating self-made reading materials related to life-long learning, which may aid in breaking down barriers in reading difficulty.

The researcher suggests allocating time to intensify the implementation of this intervention and increase the learning tools that can help students' understanding. This research suggests looking at other aspects that affect students' learning.

5. Conclusion

This study has proven that 100 Babasahin Para kay Fino is beneficial at developing students' reading comprehension. Furthermore, the teachers' self-created reading materials at Rosario National High School have been effective, successful, and interesting.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

Participants were aware of the study's goals, benefits, and risks. To do so, their privacy; details concerning them were kept confidential.

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